

FIXED OIL FROM THE SEEDS OF *ARTOCARPUS* *HIRSUTA*, LAMK

By N. S. VARIER

The oil from the seeds of *Artocarpus Hirsuta* has been chemically examined and the component acids isolated.

Artocarpus Hirsuta (Malayalam-*Anjili*) is a tree found in the ever-green forests of the west coast. The oil expressed from the seeds is used locally, in medicine and as an edible oil.

The seeds used in this work were obtained from North Travancore, each air-dried seed weighs about 0.3g. It consists of a white thin outer skin (9.6% by weight on air-dried seeds) and a kernel (90.4%) with a bitter taste. The air-dried kernel contains 17.8% moisture and 7.9% ash. The ash contains carbonate, chloride, phosphate, iron and potassium.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

18.26 G. of the air-dried powdered seeds were extracted successively in Soxlet with different solvents. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Order of extraction.	Name of solvent.	Weight	Percentage extracted.	Nature of extract
1.	Petrol (50-60°)	8.5 g.	18.17	Oil.
2.	Chloroform	0.82	1.75	Green waxy solid
3.	Ether	0.08	0.16	Thick pasty mass
4.	Ethyl acetate	0.12	0.24	
5.	Alcohol	4.10	22.46	Resinous powder.
		8.07	44.17	

The oil, obtained by extraction with petrol, had the following constants: Specific gravity at 30°=0.92; Ref. Index (30°)=1.4762; Acid value=4.0; Saponification value=179.0; Iodine value=85.05; Hehner value=91.00%; Richert Meissel value=Nil; unsaponifiable matter=1.3%

The fatty acids liberated from the oil after hydrolysis in the usual manner (Mean molecular weight, 306.9; Iodine value, 99.66) were resolved into solid (51.8%) and liquid (68.2%) acids by the lead-salt alcohol method.

A. The Liquid Acids.

Iodine value (Winkler)=113.1; mean molecular weight, 279.4. They were dissolved in ether, cooled in ice and treated, drop by drop, with bromine in glacial acetic acid (1 c. c. in 3 c.c.) till the colour of bromine was permanent. No hexabromide separated even after 24 hours. The liquid was washed with thiosulphate solution, dried, and the ether driven off. The residue was dissolved in hot petrol (50°-60°). On cooling in ice, a brown powder separated which

melted at 114° after recrystallisation from petrol and did not depress the melting point of linoleic tetrabromide.

From the filtrate the petrol was driven off when a liquid bromide resulted. This may be oleic dibromide.

Oxidation of the Liquid Acids.—The acids (2 g.) were dissolved in dilute alkali and the resulting soap was dissolved in 400 c. c. of water. To this 1.5% solution of potassium permanganate was added. It was left for 10 minutes and the excess of permanganate was destroyed by passing sulphur dioxide, when a white suspension of oxidised acids resulted. This was filtered and washed many times with water and then with a little ether. This residue was extracted with a large quantity of ether. The ether extract, after concentration, yielded a crystalline acid, m. p. 126°–28°. After recrystallisation this melted at 130°–31° and did not depress the melting point of dihydroxystearic acid. The ether-insoluble part was extracted with hot water. The hot water extract on cooling gave an acid, m. p. 162°–63°. After recrystallisation this melted at 163°–64°. Molecular weight=345.8 (tetrahydroxystearic acid Mol. wt. 348).

From the molecular weight and the m. p. it would appear that the solid is one of the tetrahydroxystearic acids.

B. The Solid Acids.

These were obtained as colourless solid with a waxy appearance, m. p. 78°–79°.

Fractional Precipitation by lead acetate.—About 5 g. of the acids were dissolved in 100 c. c. of hot alcohol and 3 c.c. of hot 10% alcoholic solution of lead acetate were added successively 5 times. The lead salt liberated in each case was decomposed by dilute nitric acid and the acids were dissolved in ether and washed and dried. The m. p. and mean molecular weights were determined in each case.

TABLE II

Fractions,	Weight.	M.p.	Mean M. W.
A ₁	1.0 g	80°	377.8
A ₂	0.5	80°	366.8
A ₃	1.8	80°	368.0
A ₄	1.0	74°	
A ₅	1.0	85–88°	

Fractions A₁, A₂ and A₃ were mixed together and recrystallised many times from alcohol yielding finally an acid, m. p. 82° (mean M. W., 332.3).

This was suspected to be cerotic acid (m. p. 78–82°, molecular weight 396) This has been confirmed by the preparation of the ethyl and methyl esters of the acid in the usual manner and by determining the molecular weight by the silver salt method. Ethyl ester, m. p. 56°, after recrystallisation from acetone m. p. 58°–59°; ethyl cerotate melts at 59° (Lewkowitch).

The acid was regenerated from the ester by boiling with alcoholic potash, m. p. 81° (mixed m. p. with original acid, 81°).

The ester distilled without decomposition under reduced pressure.

Methyl ester.—M. p. 60°; after recrystallisation from acetone, m. p. 60-61°; methyl cerotate melts at 60° (Lewkowitch). [Found (silver salt): Ag, 21.32, 21.46. $C_{26}H_{51}O_2Ag$ requires Ag, 21.47 per cent].

Fractions A₄ and A₅ were mixed together and again separated into solid and liquid acids, dissolved in alcohol and water added gradually to the solution to reprecipitate the acids. Three fractions were thus obtained.

TABLE III

Fractions.	M.p.	Mean M.W.
B ₁	78°	368.0
B ₂	57°	268.9
B ₃	59°	259.8

Fraction B₃ was recrystallised thrice from alcohol, m. p. 61° (mixed m. p. with pure palmitic acid, 61-62°).

Methyl esters of the Solid Acids.—The solid acids, prepared from a fresh quantity of the oil, were converted into methyl esters in the usual manner with 3% methyl alcoholic hydrochloric acid. After drying in vacuum, 15 g. of the esters were distilled under reduced pressure (3-5 mm.) and six fractions were obtained. All these fractions were saponified separately, the corresponding acids were liberated and these were crystallised to isolate the acids.

TABLE IV

Fractions.	B. p./3-5 mm.	Weight.	Mean M. M.	M. p. of acid.
S ₁	150-160° (boils mostly at 155°)	0.3 g.	268	60°
S ₂	170-185° (mostly at 176°)	1.05	304	66°
S ₃	180-200° (mostly at 196°)	3.50	350	74°
S ₄	200-215° (mostly at 210°)	3.1	377.6	80°
S ₅	215-230° (mostly at 225°)	3.1	390.0	82°
S ₆	230-240° (mostly at 235°)	3	392.0	82°

Unsaponifiable matter.—This was obtained as a waxy, brownish yellow mass. It gave the usual colour reactions for phytosterols.

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